

What is NuRadio?

NuRadio is an open-source, Python-based framework for the simulation, processing and reconstruction of radio detectors of ultra-high-energy (UHE, $> 10^{16}$ eV) particle cascades.

It consists of two subpackages: **NuRadioMC** [1] for Monte-Carlo simulations of in-ice radio neutrino detectors, and **NuRadioReco** [2] for data processing and reconstruction of radio detectors of high-energy neutrinos and cosmic-rays.

NuRadioMC: Simulation

1) Neutrino interaction:

Create particle cascades from flux, calculate neutrino survival probabilities, secondary interactions from ν_μ, ν_τ (using PROPOSAL).

2) Askaryan radio emission:

Simulate in-ice radio emission from particle cascade charge excess (analytic & semi-analytic models; agreement within few % with particle-level simulations).

3) Signal propagation:

Propagate radio signals through ice density profile: refraction, reflections, attenuation & birefringence.

4) Detector simulation:

Antenna & signal-chain response; trigger simulation.

NuRadioReco: Data Processing & Analysis

Data processing

Self-consistent unit system & FFTs, signal processing (e.g. bandpass filtering), computing electric-field fluence and polarization, unfolding detector effects, ...

Reconstruction algorithms

Several reconstruction algorithms allowing for e.g. end-to-end simulation & reconstruction of in-ice radio detectors for UHE neutrinos.

Why use NuRadio?

Used by many in-ice radio detector experiments (**ARIANNA**, **RNO-G**, **IceCube-Gen2**); recently also adopted by in-air radio detectors of UHE cosmic rays (**LOFAR**, **SKAO**); used in over 100 publications. Wide adoption enabled by **modularity**, **open-source** development, well-tested **reliability** and **extensive documentation**.

Modular

- Modular design: use any module stand-alone, or adapt / add individual processing modules
- Uniform interface to self-aware data classes

Open Source

- Open-source Python package developed on GitHub: github.com/nu-radio/NuRadioMC
- Over 20 contributors in past 12 months

GitHub

Reliable

All checks have passed
2 skipped, 9 successful checks

- All code subject to continuous integration (CI) tests & manual code review

Extensive documentation

- Complete API documentation & description of features at nu-radio.github.io/NuRadioMC/main.html
- Many interactive & annotated examples

Documentation

Interested? Try it out!

- To get started with NuRadio:
`pip install nuradiomc`
- Read the documentation & try the examples!

References

- [1] C. Glaser et al. *Eur. Phys. J. C* 80 (2020) doi:10.1140/epjc/s10052-020-7612-8 [1906.01670].
[2] C. Glaser et al. *Eur. Phys. J. C* 79 (2019) doi:10.1140/epjc/s10052-019-6971-5 [1903.07023]